

Millionaire profits from the War on Drugs are the reason why legalization is so difficult to achieve

*By: César Augusto Salgado
c.salgadh@uniandes.edu.co*

In the following essay, we appoint some figures that let us infer that the difficulties in legalizing drugs imposed by the policies of the United States on its war on drugs, could be due more to economic reasons than to public health motivations.

The war on drugs turns out to be as profitable a business as drug trafficking itself, and the economic groups that receive multimillion-dollar profits as contractors in its fight would pressure high governmental and legislative circles to avoid legalization. It is estimated that the annual cost of the fight against drugs is 100 billion dollars,¹ and according to the United Nations, the drug market's annual illicit drug trade would be \$330 billion.² Multiple studies show that drug legalization would break and reduce criminality and the costs associated with prosecution to minimal levels. The Global Commission on Drug Policy stated on its web page that "the war on drugs has failed and that criminalization does not reduce

¹ Count The costs. The War on Drugs: Wasting Billion and Undermining economies. Page 2. See: <https://transformdrugs.org/assets/files/PDFs/count-the-costs-economic-costs.pdf>

² Ibid.

consumption".³ Second, the data also show that the profits from the business (enormous because it is illegal) end up entering the legal market via money laundering, and therefore, for some financial conglomerates, the legalization of drugs would involve serious monetary losses.

The International Monetary Fund estimated in 1998 that "total money laundering represented 2 to 5% of the world's Gross Domestic Product. In 2009 the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime - UNODC, raised the figure to 27% of total global GDP, or 16 trillion dollars."⁴

Illegality drives up the price of drugs: "For economists and businessmen, this is a predictable outcome. Limiting the supply of products in high demand through repression dramatically increases their price, creating an opportunity and profit motive for criminal entrepreneurs to enter the trade. Prices are further inflated, as they reflect the risk faced by suppliers ".⁵

In the multimillion-dollar business of fighting drug trafficking, state and private security contractors end up producing more violence than they want to stop. The objective of the services provided by the security forces is to reduce drug supply and consumption, in addition to weakening the criminal organizations that produce violence by reducing the crime rate.

³ See: <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-un-drugs-idUSKCN0HV1M420141006>

⁴ NODC, 'Estimating illicit financial flows transnational organized crimes', 2011, p 5. See: https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/Studies/Illicit_financial_flows_2011_web.pdf.

⁵ Count The costs. The War on Drugs: Wasting Billion and Undermining economies. Page 3. See: <https://transformdrugs.org/assets/files/PDFs/count-the-costs-economic-costs.pdf>

However, despite the exorbitant expenditure that these services cost, production, supply, consumption, and violence grow exponentially. "In Colombia, for example, defense spending increased from 3.6% of GDP in 2003 to 6% in 2006. This resulted in a real increase in the security forces from 250,000 (150,000 military and 100,000 police) to 850,000 over the four years."⁶

The drug enforcement budget in the Obama administration nearly doubled from \$15.3 billion in 2009 to \$31 billion in 2017. "Since 2008, taxpayers in the United States have contributed nearly \$213 billion through the National Drug Control Strategy efforts and this figure includes funds that went to law enforcement, treatment, and prevention, as well as resources to combat drug trafficking."⁷ The question to be answered is: Who keeps this money, how this money is distributed, which companies provide their services under contract in the war on drugs, and for how much?

In 2011 *Wired* magazine reported that a single unnamed Pentagon agency, the Defense Department's Counter-Narcoterrorism Program Office, known as the CNTPO, handled \$3 billion in contracts ranging "from training Mexican helicopter pilots to mentoring Azeri naval commandos to designing websites for the Pakistani government."⁸ Anything that sounds like counter-narcoterrorism can be contracted by this office. The concern about this office is not only because of

⁶ Keefer, P and Loayza, N, op cit, p13.

⁷ See: <https://www.monarchshores.com/drug-addiction/how-much-does-the-war-on-drugs-cost/>

⁸ See: <https://www.wired.com/2011/11/drug-war-mercenary/>

the huge budget but also because through these agreements the agency ends up hiring mercenaries for security work in other countries, as we will see below. The organization, headed by civilian Mike Strand since 1995, has contracted with Blackwater's subsidiary, U.S. Training, as well as with "Lockheed Martin, Northrop Grumman, Raytheon and ARINC for a wide range of defense counter-drug activities."⁹

In his article "Privatizing the War on Drugs," Christopher Hobson describes the emergence of military and security companies (PMSC)¹⁰ by showing how the use of these companies contractors futilely and expensively furthers the war on drugs, and argues that there is a need to move from a prohibitionist to an alternative approach, and asserts that *the use of private military and security companies (PMSCs) creates a strong interest in maintaining the increasingly problematic and costly status quo that is counter- narcotics.*¹¹

To make a serious case that drug legalization is stalled in the U.S. legislature and executive for reasons of lobbying by private military and security companies, it would be necessary to establish a history of the profits and names of these companies over the course of the Drug War.¹² Hobson shows how these companies began to acquire an increasingly

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Private military and security companies (PMSC)

¹¹ Hobson, Christopher. Privatizing the war on drugs. *Third World Quarterly*, 2014. Page 1141. Vol. 35, No. 8, 1441-1456, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2014.946261>

¹² Hobson notes that the literature on the subject is growing rapidly. "For a complete list of resources, see the "Articles, Reports and Statistics" section of the "Private Security Monitor" page hosted by Denver University. http://psm.du.edu/articles_reports_statistics/index.html."

important role during the 1990s and came to play a fundamental role after the wars in Afghanistan and Iraq.

Information is scarce, and Hobson recounts that even at the first hearing held by the Committee on Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs, representatives of the State Department and the Department of Defense had problems providing simple facts and figures.

It was discovered that the State did not have a centralized database to collect the contracts, and to everyone's surprise, "the Department of Defense admitted -without any blush for sarcasm-, that they had to spend another \$50,000 on contractors to collect the requested information."¹³

In 2010, the U.S. State Department received more than \$1 billion for international counternarcotics assistance programs, 90% of which went to five countries: Mexico, Afghanistan, Colombia, Peru and Bolivia. Much of that budget was used for contractors, mainly for aerial eradication and interdiction.¹⁴ Between 2005 and 2009, the United States spent more than US\$3.1 billion on counter-narcotics contracts in Latin America.

After fifty years of drug war policy, and with an illegal narcotics market that has not been undermined, Hobson says the use of private security contractors makes drug policy reform more difficult and tips the balance in maintaining a militarized approach, perpetuating the problem.

¹³ Hobson, Christopher. Privatizing the war on drugs. *Third World Quarterly*, 2014. Page 1142. Vol. 35, No. 8, 1441-1456, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2014.946261>

¹⁴ *Ibid*, p. 1443.

Of the 6100 million dollars given in assistance by the United States for the named Plan Colombia between 2000 and 2008, "70% of the money was spent on military equipment and contractors, with DynCorp being the largest beneficiary."¹⁵ From 11 companies contracted by the U.S. for counter-narcotics in 2002, the number increased to 25 in 2006. "Between 2005 and 2009, the U.S. spent more than \$1.9 billion in counter-narcotics contracts in Colombia, with the majority going to just five companies: DynCorp, Lockheed Martin, Raytheon, ITT, and ARINC. Of these, DynCorp was by far the largest, receiving some \$1.1 billion in contracts throughout the Latin American region. In 2006, the company received \$164 million in contracts in Colombia, a quarter of the entire aid budget for the country's military and police that year."¹⁶

As one delves deeper into the role of private military and security companies (PMSCs) it all leads to one point: the privatization of the war on drugs. While this is already the case with modern warfare, the entry of a major economic player into the drug war makes it a market issue. On the other hand, there is also concern about the sovereignty and geopolitical control of the United States in the region and the use of mercenaries with full immunity.

While the Washington Consensus believes that privatization saves money, the cost-benefit of contracting private military security companies is cost-ineffective. But on the other hand, a major concern lies in the minimal oversight and control over these taxpayer monies. It seems like a broken sack of millions

¹⁵ Ibid, p. 1444.

¹⁶ Ibid.

of dollars going nowhere. DynCorp was forced to return 40 million dollars for incorrect billing and duplicate payments.¹⁷

The congressional subcommittee cited for oversight of the PMSCs in 2010 concluded that "neither the State Department nor the Department of Defense has adequate systems in place to track counter drug contract data" and that, "while spending on counter drug contracts increased by 32% during the five years under review, contract management and oversight had been inadequate."¹⁸

Money laundering legalizing illicit gains

We have cited some data on the profits that military contractors in the fight against drugs receive, which would allow us to ask whether part of the refusal of the United States to legalize drugs comes from particular interests, such as those of these contractors. As mentioned above, it would be necessary to investigate 1) the names of the contractors, 2) the amounts of the contracts, and 3) whether they have lobbied Congress to maintain the repressive policy of the war on drugs.

Examples of the influence of private and large corporations on issues of public interest abound. To cite just a handful of cases, the National Rifle Association's (NRA) lobbying to keep the carrying of guns, including assault rifles and automatic and

¹⁷ Ibid, p. 1449.

¹⁸ Ibid.

semi-automatic weapons unchecked, despite the public health epidemic that shootings and massacres in the U.S. have become¹⁹.

Another example could be, as the New York Times headlined, "the fight in Colombia to tax sugary drinks "²⁰. An economic group that lobbies at the behest of Congress -with some anonymous confessions of congressmen acknowledging bribes-, so that their business is not taxed with duties that could discourage the consumption of their product, but instead reduce public health problems and lower the number of citizens with diabetes and other diseases related to high sugar consumption. *(Cite how much diabetes patients cost to Colombia).*

Large corporations with their immense financial power have become a threat to the spirit of representation of democracy. Now a senator or representative to the chamber does not necessarily defend the interests of the citizens who elect him or her, but of the big corporations that with their money can influence the elections of congressmen who defend their interests and who end up being press chiefs for the big corporations. It is no longer the power by and for the people, but the power by and for Capital. Would this be happening with the obtuse and stubborn refusal to legalize drugs by the United States, and the obsequious and timid reaction of the countries that suffer the most from the consequences of this war, such as Colombia or Mexico?

¹⁹ See: <https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2022/05/senate-state-bias-filibuster-blocking-gun-control-legislation/638425/>

²⁰ See: <https://www.nytimes.com/es/2017/11/13/espanol/america-latina/colombia-impuesto-bebidas-azucaradas-obesidad.html>

The second case that arouses suspicions of private interests in the stubborn idea of maintaining the war on drugs, making private interests prevail over public health and the general interest, is the laundering of money by financial conglomerates.

Although the market is gigantic, only 2.6% of the total street value of cocaine produced there remains within Colombia. The other 97.4% of the profits are harvested by criminal syndicates, and laundered by banks in consumer countries.”²¹

If the annual market for illicit drugs is 330 billion dollars and part of that money is laundered through banks, how much would the price of drugs drop and, therefore, how much money would they stop earning if drugs were legalized and the smaller profits no longer go to laundering but to the State's coffers via taxes?

In 2010, Wachovia Bank allowed the laundering of \$3784 million into Mexican exchange house accounts. According to the federal prosecutor in the case: "Wachovia's blatant disregard for our banking laws gave the cocaine cartels carte blanche to finance their operations.”²² It didn't turn out to be bad business for the bank in the illicit transaction, apparently. "Wachovia paid federal authorities \$110 million in forfeiture and received a \$50 million fine for failing to control the cash used to transport

²¹ Gaviria, A and Mejia, D (Eds), *Anti-Drugs Policies In Colombia: Successes, Failures And Wrong Turns*, Ediciones Uniandes, 2011.

²² Count The costs. *The War on Drugs: Wasting Billion and Undermining economies*. Page 9. See: <https://transformdrugs.org/assets/files/PDFs/count-the-costs-economic-costs.pdf>

22 tons of cocaine.”²³ The fines represented "less than 2% of the bank's profits in 2009.²⁴

HSBC was fined \$19 billion in 2012 for complicity in money laundering by failing to monitor \$670 billion in transactions in Mexico.²⁵ In another case, Mexican and Colombian cartels laundered \$881 million through HSBC and "the U.S. Justice Department did not file criminal charges against the executives because the size of the bank's assets and investments could destabilize the global financial system.

When you are that rich you don't face charges. Money laundering is of such monumental proportions that even the laundering proceeds saved the banks from the 2008 crisis, and according to Antonio Maria Costa, the head of the UNODC, "there was strong evidence that funds from drug trafficking and other criminal activities were the only liquid investment capital available to some banks at the time. Interbank loans were financed with money that originated in the drug trade, and there were signs that some banks were bailed out in this way.”²⁶

The profits of private military and security companies (PMSCs) providing counter-narcotics services are so high, along with the monumental financial returns from the laundering of drug money by banks, that one might wonder if the stubborn stance of the U.S. drug war is due to pressure and lobbying by these economic groups to keep the illegal business going, to continue

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ *Ibid.*

the business of fighting drug trafficking, and to keep prices high to maintain higher financial returns through money laundering. But we will talk about lobbying later.

The most expensive failure in history

With inflation adjusted for today, War World II cost four trillion dollars.²⁷ It was four years, from 1941 to 1945, after Japan attacked Pearl Harbor and then President Franklin D. Roosevelt asked Congress on December 8th, 1941, a declaration of war for the "unprovoked and dastardly attack."

Declarations are declarations and all of them have their solemnity. On June 17, 1971, President Nixon announced the War on Drugs.²⁸ Since then, this combat has cost 1 trillion dollars.²⁹ The Second World War was brutal, a dark moment in human history. After its end, it left the United States in a privileged economic and political position as a world power. Since the War on Drugs started, and despite its one trillion dollars expended, the results show the rise in consumers, the increase in drug prices, and the exponential enrichment of criminal organizations dedicated to the sale and trafficking of drugs.

²⁷ See: [https://online.norwich.edu/cost-us-wars-then-and-now#:~:text=Though it lasted less than,gross domestic product \(GDP\).](https://online.norwich.edu/cost-us-wars-then-and-now#:~:text=Though it lasted less than,gross domestic product (GDP).)

²⁸ <https://time.com/6090016/us-war-on-drugs-origins/#>

²⁹ See: <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/06/17/the-us-has-spent-over-a-trillion-dollars-fighting-war-on-drugs.html>

Reducing consumption by blocking supply from producer countries has had the opposite result, and instead of fewer users, there are now more. According to the U.S. Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, by 2019 the number of drug users rose 13% in Americans over the age of 12, reaching a 40-year high.³⁰

In just one year, the number of overdose deaths went from 70,630 in 2019 to 90,000 in 2020.³¹ The billion-dollar bet has been a resounding failure. In 2016, twenty-four million Americans over the age of 12 were by that time marijuana users (9% of the population.)³² Some four million Americans (1.5% of the population) had problematic marijuana use. In 2020, five million Americans were cocaine users at that time, almost 2% of the population.³³

According to the National Center for Health Statistics³⁴, "about 92,000 people died in the United States in 2020 from overdoses, including illicit drugs and prescription opioids."³⁵ Nixon's war on drugs went after cocaine, heroin, and marijuana, but left out the use of legal opioids, which are the real culprits of the public health epidemic in the United States.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Ibid

³³ See: <https://www.cdc.gov/drugoverdose/deaths/other-drugs.html>

³⁴ National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS). <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/>.

³⁵ See: <https://nida.nih.gov/research-topics/trends-statistics/overdose-death-rates>

According to the CATO Institute, "In 1980, for example, 580,900 people were arrested on drug-related charges in the United States. By 2014, that number had increased to 1,561,231. More than 700,000 of these arrests in 2014 were related to marijuana. Nearly half of the 186,000 people serving time in federal prisons in the United States are incarcerated on drug-related charges."³⁶ And quoting an article from Peter Wagner and Wendy Sawyer about mass incarceration, "every 25 seconds, someone in America is arrested for drug possession. The number of Americans arrested for possession has tripled since 1980, reaching 1.3 million arrests per year in 2015-six times the number of arrests for drug sales."³⁷

The anti-drug strategy promises to reduce consumption and end criminal organizations such as cartels. Its promise has failed for 50 years. Many of the grandchildren of those who smoked marijuana when Nixon declared the new war are now smoking more potent marijuana. Three generations, grandparents, parents, and children, have paid part of that trillion dollars with their taxes.

Despite the resounding failure of the war on drugs, U.S. taxpayers and voters still accept and support their government

³⁶ See: https://www.cato.org/policy-analysis/four-decades-counting-continued-failure-war-drugs#_idTextAnchor005. Citing: Federal Bureau of Prisons, U.S. Department of Justice, "Prisoners in 2015," December 2016, <https://www.bjs.gov/content/pub/pdf/p15.pdf>; Drug Policy Alliance, "Drug War Statistics," 2016, <http://www.drugpolicy.org/drug-war-statistics>; and Drug War Facts, "Crime, Arrests, and US Law Enforcement," 2016, <http://www.drugwarfacts.org/cms/Crime#sthash.YB72ynK2.uGixEd5.dpbs>.

³⁷ See: <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/ending-war-drugs-numbers/>. Citing: Peter Wagner and Wendy Sawyer, "Mass Incarceration: The Whole Pie 2018" (Northampton, MA: Prison Policy Initiative, 2018), available at <https://www.prisonpolicy.org/reports/pie2018.html>

spending money to combat drug trafficking in producer countries.

Why then do legislators continue to stubbornly pass failed bills that perpetuate the war on drugs, instead of legalizing and regulating it? If consumption increases and violence increases, why then do the taxpayers who pay for this lost strategy continue to support the war on drugs?

"Lockheed Martin commissioned pollster Mark Mellman to conduct a survey that showed voters were inclined to blame Democrats for the rise in drug use and that this could be the Achilles heel in the 2000 election. The poll showed that 56% of voters agreed with a \$2 billion increase in funding for tracking planes to be used in drug-producing areas."³⁸

- Show how the war on drugs increases violence ' Dead in Colombian fields ' dead in Mexico.

Despite the resounding failure of the drug war policy, legislators continue to support it. Rather than addicted to failure, "they are addicted to budgetary success, in the sense that they have been enormously successful in their enduring ability to increase the drug war budget."³⁹13. In 2010 about 60% of the Obama administration's counternarcotics budget, about \$10 billion out of \$15 billion, went to supply reduction rather than demanda.⁴⁰

³⁸ Ibid, page 32.

³⁹ Ibid, p. 21.

⁴⁰ Ibid, p. 22.

In 2014 that same law *enforcement* budget increased to \$25 billion "even though the United States continued to be the world's largest consumer of illicit substances."⁴¹ The Trump administration "increased spending on interdiction by 9.9% and reduced prevention spending by 11.1% relative to the 2017 levels."⁴² Notwithstanding the stubborn and continued focus on reducing supply and not demand through repression, "empirical studies have shown that for every dollar invested in demand reduction strategies, taxpayers save \$7.86 in social costs."⁴³

Campaign finance: who finances them and what are they financed for?

Fighting drugs is big business.

Horace Bartilow describes very well the relationship between the passage of repressive anti-drug policies by legislators and the financing of their political campaigns by security contractor companies. Published in 2019, his book is called "Drug War Pathologies"⁴⁴, and in chapter II analyzes the case of the approval of the Plan Colombia and Plan Merida. Bartilow offers

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Ibid. Author citing (Miron and Waldock, 2010).

⁴⁴ Bartilow, Horace. *Drug War Pathologies : Embedded Corporatism and U.S. Drug Enforcement in the Americas*. Chapter 2. Drug War profiteer. U.S. Enforcement Decision Making and Plan Colombia and the Merida Initiative. See: <https://academic.oup.com/north-carolina-scholarship-online/book/31502/chapter-abstract/264831103?redirectedFrom=fulltext>

a theoretical explanation as to why this collusion between security contractors, the state budget, and political campaign financing occurs. We will not dwell on his explanation, but the figures he offers are revealing.

The Plan Colombia was originally conceived as an economic and social development project to close the inequity gaps that fueled not only poverty but also the armed conflict with insurgent guerrillas. Through development programs, manual eradication of coca crops, substitution of illicit crops, and infrastructure development such as roads and loans, the programs sought to offer alternatives to the cultivation of coca leaves that served as an input for cocaine production.

The plan, as originally conceived, did not find support in the United States. However, a new plan emerged (originally drafted in English and which took many months to be translated into Spanish, which says a lot about who wrote it first). The European Union had pledged \$750 million to contribute to the original plan, but after the United States intervened in a new plan with a military component, the European Union withdrew from the program.

This is where Bartilow weaves some connections:

The Congressional Black Caucus, an umbrella group for African-American members of Congress, supported Plan Colombia, not because "its members received campaign contributions to corporations (...) or because they represented districts where corporate factories generated jobs. The

Congressional Black Caucus supported it because of political strategy.”⁴⁵

Insofar as corporations enjoy a "privileged position" in government, "it is reflected in the way corporations influenced congressional support for Plan Colombia. That influence was exercised through well-funded lobbying and through the ability of corporations to generate jobs that would produce the military equipment needed for the plan (*Plan Colombia*) in the districts of those members of Congress who might vote against the measure.”⁴⁶ Corporate power is also reflected in the so-called "revolving door" in which members of the elite move into the government bureaucracy. Also, in the financing of campaigns for members of Congress.

According to Bartilow, "US corporations collectively lobbied for Plan Colombia through the USCBP⁴⁷ (...) which represents a coalition of industries (in the fields) of energy, pharmaceuticals, financial services, technology, insurance, defense and security, and transportation.”⁴⁸

Oil, gas and mining companies that lobbied to increase the security of their investments, security companies took advantage of Plan Colombia's military focus on reducing cocaine production in Colombia.

⁴⁵ Ibid, p. 26.

⁴⁶ Ibid, p. 29.

⁴⁷ I was unable to find any additional information on the USCBP other than that in this book.

⁴⁸ Ibid, p. 29.

There is a large pipeline to move the oil from the extraction area to the port or refining plant. That pipeline is called Caño Limón - Coveñas and 98 million dollars were authorized for its security. "ExxonMobile, Texaco, and Britain's BP Amoco, together spent \$13 million on lobbying in the years before the approval of Plan Colombia."⁴⁹ Drummon, which managed the La Loma coal mine, lobbied for support for the security of its mine from guerrilla attacks and kidnappings. Enron owned 43% of Promigas and lobbied for the protection of its gas line.

Likewise, "Lockheed Martin lobbied members of Congress to include in the bill an order to purchase its Orion P-2 airborne radars, used to track drug shipments, and also its K-Max helicopters, used for drug interdiction"⁵⁰ United Technologies Corporation, which is headquartered in Hartford, Connecticut, and produces the Black Hawk helicopter, lobbied members of Congress who were not committed to supporting the Colombia plan and between 1996 and 2000 spent \$8 million on congressional lobbying."

One example offered by Professor Bartilow is the case of Connecticut State Senators Christopher Dodd, an opponent of military intervention in Latin America, and Joseph Lieberman. United Technologies manufactures Blackhawk helicopters in Connecticut and generate many jobs in its voting region, plus continued campaign support for those senators, and Dodd became an advocate for Plan Colombia and "reintroduced an amendment that put the Blackhawk back in, which had been removed from the version of the bill. The amendment failed,

⁴⁹ Citing Aviles 2006 - Page 30

⁵⁰ Ibid, p. 32. The author cites (Isikoff, 2000).

but Dodd succeeded in keeping the Blackhawk funding below \$110 millions.⁵¹

When keeping inmates in prison is good business for someone

One in five people in prison is incarcerated for drug-related offenses. If the fight against drugs has cost a trillion dollars, imprisoning people costs \$182 billion a year in USA.⁵² "Mass incarceration leaves a heavy burden on both the federal and state government's budgets. The Prison Policy Initiative, a think tank, and criminal justice advocacy group, found that 1 in 5 currently incarcerated people in the U.S. are locked up for a drug offense. The same research estimates that it costs an average of about \$37,500 annually⁵³ to house an inmate in federal correctional facilities and that mass incarceration costs the U.S. at least \$182 billion every year."⁵⁴

In regarding the costs, "some states, like Indiana have managed to keep prices low at around \$14,000 per inmate. While states like New York pay around \$60,000 to keep its citizens behind

⁵¹ Ibid, p. 32.

⁵² See: <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/06/17/the-us-has-spent-over-a-trillion-dollars-fighting-war-on-drugs.html>

⁵³ Cited in the article: <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2019/11/19/2019-24942/annual-determination-of-average-cost-of-incarceration-fee-coif>.

⁵⁴ <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/06/17/the-us-has-spent-over-a-trillion-dollars-fighting-war-on-drugs.html>

bars.”⁵⁵ But if these figures don't say too much, one can hear the words from Thierry Godard in regarding the economics of the American prison system: It is so massive, "that its estimated turnover of \$74 billion eclipses the GDP of 133 nations.”⁵⁶ And because privatized prisons get 10% of the expenses, they take \$7.4 billion per year. ⁵⁷ Only the profits of two companies in the US prison business, Corrections Corporation of America and GEO Group, "generated over \$2.53 billion in revenue in 2012, and represent more than half of the private prison business.”⁵⁸

In his talk for CBU in 2016, philosopher and Yale University professor Jason Stanley showed the relationship between racism, drugs, and privatization of prisons.⁵⁹ In his talk, he showed how the incarceration rate in the United States is 756 per 100,000 inhabitants, while France has 70 per 100,000 inhabitants, and England, with large doses of alcohol involved, has 150 per 100,000. Stanley showed that the second country with the second highest rate of incarceration at that time was Russia (a non-liberal democracy) with 500 prisoners per 100,000 inhabitants, a "level of incarceration similar to the number of people sent to the gulag during the height of Stalin's regime. Twenty-five percent of the world's prisoners are in the United States.

⁵⁵ <https://smartasset.com/mortgage/the-economics-of-the-american-prison-system#> 30 Ibid.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ See: Propaganda, race and mass incarceration with Dr. Jason Stanley. See: [https:// www.youtube.com/watch?v=lnYKCKJtA8s&t=12s](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lnYKCKJtA8s&t=12s)

13% of the U.S. population is black or African-American. About 38 million Americans are African American. From 1980 to 2006, the incarceration rate of African Americans in the United States grew four times that of whites.⁶⁰

While in 1968 15% of African American adults had been convicted of a felony and 7% had been sent to prison. In 2004 the numbers rose to 33% of African American adults convicted of a felony and 17% sent to prison. In other words, in just over thirty years, the percentage of African-American adults who had been convicted of a felony had doubled, as well those sent to prison.⁶¹

There is also a massive racial disparity that comes with drug incarcerations. According to the Drug Policy Alliance, nearly 80% of the people in federal prison and almost 60% of people in state prison for drug offenses are Black or Latino. In 2019, despite making up just 13.4% of the U.S. population, the FBI reported that more than a quarter of the drug-related arrests were of Black American adults.

Consumption is in the north, but violence is in the south.

The business of selling weapons to Mexico and blaming them for violence

⁶⁰ Ibid

⁶¹ See also: <https://news.uga.edu/total-us-population-with-felony-convictions/>

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Count The costs. The War on Drugs: Wasting Billion and Undermining economies. Pag 2. See: <https://transformdrugs.org/assets/files/PDFs/count-the-costs-economic-costs.pdf>
2. UNODC, 'Estimating illicit financial flows transnational organized crimes', 2011, p 5. See: https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/Studies/Illicit_financial_flows_2011_web.pdf.
3. Keefer, P and Loayza, N, op cit, p13.
4. How Much Does the War on Drugs Cost?. See: [https://www.monarchshores.com/drug-addiction/how-much-does-the-war-](https://www.monarchshores.com/drug-addiction/how-much-does-the-war-on-drugs-cost/)
5. [on-drugs-cost/](https://www.monarchshores.com/drug-addiction/how-much-does-the-war-on-drugs-cost/)
6. Pentagon's war on drugs goes mercenary. Wired. See: <https://www.wired.com/2011/11/drug-war-mercenary/>
7. Hobson, Christopher. Privatizing the war on drugs. Third World
8. Quarterly, 2014. Pg 1141. Vol. 35, No. 8, 1441-1456, [http://](http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2014.946261)
9. dx.doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2014.946261

12. The Real Reason America Doesn't Have Gun Control. The Atlantic.
13. [https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2022/05/senate-state-](https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2022/05/senate-state-bias-filibuster-blocking-gun-control-legislation/638425/)
14. [bias-filibuster-blocking-gun-control-legislation/638425/](https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2022/05/senate-state-bias-filibuster-blocking-gun-control-legislation/638425/)
15. "We were silenced": Colombia's fight to tax sugary drinks. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/es/2017/11/13/english/america-latina/colombia-tax-sugar-sweetened-beverages-obesity.html>.
16. Gaviria, A and Mejia, D (Eds), Anti-Drugs Policies In Colombia:
17. Successes, Failures And Wrong Turns, Ediciones Uniandes, 2011.
18. Drug money saved banks in global crisis, claims UN advisor', The Observer, 13/12/09. See: [https://www.theguardian.com/global/2009/](https://www.theguardian.com/global/2009/dec/13/drug-money-banks-saved-un-chief-claims)
19. [dec/13/drug-money-banks-saved-un-chief-claims](https://www.theguardian.com/global/2009/dec/13/drug-money-banks-saved-un-chief-claims)